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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This research work focuses attention on the geological properties of a hydrocarbon bearing in 'Eme' field of the Niger Delta. The environment of deposition is examined and the type produced as a model of the sub-surface reservoir. To achieve this, an integrated analysis of cores from wells, as well as biostratigraphic data and wireline logs of the D7.000 sand were used for the study. The D7.000 sand of study comprises one major depositional sequence. It is made up of upper and lower stratigraphic para-sequence sets. The upper depositional setting is interpreted as transgressive sand deposits in an estuarine environment. However, the lower depositional setting is interpreted as progradational deposits. Hence, the depositional model interpreted for the reservoir sand is prograding marine shoreface followed by a transgressive estuarine setting. This shows that a period of regression was followed by a transgressive phase which led to the deposition of the estuarine complexes. From the petrophysical study carried out through use of composite logs, amalgamated sand is found to be more porous and more permeable than the tidal channel. Core analysis revealed the existence of ten lithofacies. These lithofacies are grouped into facies association in a vertical sequence with a genetic significance using primary structures and shape of wireline logs.

Keywords: sequence, stratigraphy, Niger Delta, paleoenvironmental, Eme, D.7000 sand.

INTRODUCTION

D7.000 sand comprises multi-storey sand bodies and heterolithic mixture of sand shale. These sand bodies have good reservoir quality, while the heterolithics have reservoir quality and act as baffles to vertical flow of hydrocarbon. Thus, this cause production problem in the D7.000 sand. The research work is intended to unravel the sequence stratigraphy of the D7.000 sand through the existing approach of use of cores and wireline logs. The overall depositional character of the D7.000 reflects the Petrophysical problems. Production problems could be field wide or peculiar to the Niger Delta depobelt. Porosity and permeability in the D7.000 sand are affected by the grain size distribution, clay composition, bioturbation, cementation and compaction. For example, there is a decrease in porosity and permeability in the area where shale content is relatively high. Therefore, the top and bottom parts of the D7.000 sand a baffle to flow of hydrocarbon. Different depositional environments are characterized by a peculiar Petrophysical identity which varies with the rock type, lithofacies type and reflect variety of pore geometry present.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are: To provide a detailed geological description of the reservoir (D7.000) sand. Ascertain the permeability and porosity values and evaluate the reservoir potential of D7.000 sand. To reconstruct the environment of deposition and provide a depositional model suitable for the reservoir sand. Determine the sequence stratigraphic setting of the D7.000 sand and provide a genetic unit classification for the reservoir sand.

Location of the Study Area

The hydrocarbon bearing (D7.000) sand is located in the 'Eme' field of the central depobelt of the Niger delta. The field is very close to the Nun river, about 110 west of Port Harcourt (fig 1). It lies between latitudes 5° and 6° N, and longitudes 6° and 7° E.

Geology of the Study Area

Stratigraphy: Well sections in the Niger Delta indicate three vertical lithostratigraphic subdivisions. Benin Formation which is an upper delta top lithofacies consisting of massive continental sands and gravels, grades downwards into delta front lithofacies of the Agbada Formation. The Agbada Formation comprises mostly shoreface and channels with minor alternation of sand and shales in equal proportion at the lower part. Below Agbada Formation is Akata Formation which is a prodelta marine shale sited in a relatively deep marine setting (Reijers, 1996). The thickness of the Benin Formation ranges from 0-6000ft and is the source of the water supply. The Agbada Formation contains the hydrocarbon reservoirs while the over pressured shales of the Akata Formation is a source of hydrocarbon generation.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

There are three methods of study used in the analysis of the D7.000 sand. They are core description, the use of wireline logs and biostratigraphic data interpretation.

Core Description: The analysis of the reservoir (D7. 000) sand involves the use of integrated cores from wells 6 and 7 taken from the top to bottom of the D7.000 sand. The total length of cores described for the two wells are about 292ft and 321ft respectively. Core is described in terms of the primary sedimentary structures, bioturbation, grain sizes, sorting, colour, diagenetic processes as well as lithology.

Primary Sedimentary Structures; Pettijon and Potter (1964) defined primary sedimentary structures as those formed at time of deposition or shortly thereafter and before consolidation of the sediments in which they are found. These sedimentary structures are as a result of physical, chemical and biological processes occurring in an environment. Based on the processes of formation of these sedimentary structures, lithofacies are classified.

Wireline logs: Use of wireline log data to guide and constrain the sedimentological interpretation of the cored sequences is employed. In order to ascertain the porosity and permeability values of the reservoir sand, a composite log is used. These include gamma ray log, bulk density log and resistivity log.

RESULTS/INTERPRETATION

Core Results: Core results of wells 6 & 7 indicate that the lithofacies are commonly sandstone/shale alternations or sequences. See (Plate 1-10), some of the parameters used in identifying the lithofacies are as follows:

- (a) **Grain Sizes:** Visually, the grain size distribution falls within the range of very fine to coarse grain hence, bedding surfaces are recognized mostly by abrupt vertical changes in sizes and sometimes gradational changes occur. One of the intervals where abrupt vertical changes occur is seen in well 6 at a depth of 12256ft. Generally, there is mostly a decrease in grains sizes with an increase in depth from the lower half of the reservoir sand as seen in both wells 6&7 at a depth of (12312-12442) ft and (11972-12142) ft, respectively.
- (b) **Sorting:** This is the tendency of mineral grains in a particular rock to approach uniformity in size. However, it ranges from well sorting to poor sorting in the field of study. In well 6 for example, there is well -sorted very fine grain materials between (12438- 12443) ft. Conversely, poorly sorted grains are seen at the upper part of the same well at a depth interval of (12299-12305) ft. The well -sorted zone in the wells contains shales, while the poor sorted parts constitute a mixture of different sizes of grain materials.

- (c) **Colour:** There are varieties of grey colours seen while examining the cores. Colour ranges from light grey to dark grey. For example, at the distal end of the two cored wells, the colour is found to be dark grey shale which is an indication of the presence of organic matter.

Sedimentary Structures

Various kind of sedimentary structures are seen through physical examination of cores from well 6 & 7. These include, planar cross bedding, current ripple marks, lenticular bedding, rootlets, hummocky cross stratification, reactivation surface and many more. These inorganic primary sedimentary structures are produced as a result of interactions between the physical and biological characteristics of the sediment and the fluid, gravity, as well as the hydraulic environment.

(i). **Planar cross bedding:** Planar cross bedding occurs in the field. It is defined as a cross-bedded unit whose bounding surfaces form more or less planar surfaces and is a sedimentary structure which occurs in sand horizons as seen in the core samples. Though, they occur as small scale cross bedding ranging in size from a few centimeters to about 4cm in thickness. A planar grain lineation is equally identified and shows a differentiation of colour banding and uniqueness in size (Plate 1).

(ii). **Current ripple marks:** Current ripple is observed in the field of study at a depth of 12223ft of well 6. This bedding plane structure occurs mostly in sedimentary depositions below wave base. From the Core description of wells 6 & 7 of the reservoir of study in 'Eme' field, current ripple marks are observed to occur mainly in fine-grained sandy heterolith. Ripples produce a small scale cross bedding (ripple bedding) on migration. Rippled sandstones are draped by wavy dark-grey mudstones, asymmetrical with a gentle slope or down current slope. Hence, a good criterion used in interpreting the direction of current flow.

(iii). **Lenticular bedding:** In the field of study, there are portions where mud dominates the sand particles. This forms the wavy-muddy heterolith. The mud lenticles coalesce resulting in wavy bedding. However, with the dominance of the mud, the ripple bedded sand units are isolated and embedded in the mud matrix thereby giving rise to lenticular bedding. There are no load structures seen in this portion in spite of their high probability of occurrence.

(iv). **Hummocky Cross-Stratification:** Hummocky cross-stratification shows a low angle dipping bedding pattern. Also, there are concave upward swales which are characteristics of upper shoreface setting or storm dominated environment. Hummocky cross stratification is characterized by erosional lower bounding surfaces dipping mostly at less than 10° , with laminae almost parallel to the lower bounding surface.

(v). **Rootlets:** These are vertical carbonaceous materials or openings at uppermost part of the core samples observed as inlet through which small root sizes grow. They are seen in some dark shales. Rootlets are abundant in the zone which signifies evidence of plant life and continental deposition.

(vi) **Bioturbation Structures:** There are some organic sedimentary structures seen while examining the core such as bioturbation structures produced by benthonic communities which provide useful information regarding conditions of sedimentation. There are also dominance of interpenetrating burrows while Planolites, Ophiomorpha nodosa and rare fossil shell remains are encountered in some places. However, from the physical examination of the cores, bioturbation activity increases with depth, hence, is high in very quiet environment of sandy heterolith. At a depth of 12443ft, the deposit constitutes a massive-bedded mudstone with small rippled siltstone in between the grey mudstones, and rare to barren in trace fossils.

Lithofacies Description

Lithofacies are identified based on core description and log shape of the reservoir D7.000 sand in 'Eme' field. Individual lithofacies are composed of different types of sedimentary structures and may be distinguished by the presence of bedding units with a characteristic sedimentary structure, a limited grain size range, a certain bed thickness, perhaps a distinctive texture or colour.

Plate 1- Planar laminated sandstone

LITHOFACIES 1: Planar laminated sandstone. The lithofacies, planar laminated sandstone comprises fine to medium sand particles. It is moderately to well sorted, grey in colour and consists of planar grain lineation of coarse and medium grains which form laminae on foresets (Plate 1). The lithofacies is about 2cm to 4cm thick, it has an erosional relationship with overlying lithofacies coarse grained cross bedded sandstone and gradational relationship with underlying lithofacies wave rippled sandstone. However, very fine grains of mud are conspicuously absent and there is no presence of bioturbation activities in this lithofacies. In essence, it is an indication of high energy or shallow marine environment.

Plate 2-Current rippled sandstone

Lithofacies 2: Current-rippled sandstone. The lithofacies consists of fine to medium grain sandstones with some coarse grain materials found at the base. It is moderately sorted. There are no wavy beds and has a clay content but low angle cross-beds exist. The rippled sandstone is draped by wavy, dark grey mudstone which is asymmetrical with a gentle slope, an indication of current direction. (Plate 2). The lithofacies contains a sporadic bioturbation traces though traces of Planolites and ichnofacies is common with scanty Skolithos traces. This type of lithofacies is likely to occur in fluvial or shallow marine environment. Hence, tidal channel or tidal flat are the likely potential origin of this facies.

Plate 3-Bioturbated Sandstone.

Lithofacie 3: Bioturbated sandstone. Sandstones in this lithofacies constitute very fine- to- fine grains. Though, medium grains are encountered sporadically. It is well sorted with discontinuous carbonaceous laminae. There is also very little clay content with the absence of primary sedimentary structures as a result of intensive bioturbation activities. Furthermore, the dominance of interpenetrating burrows of *Ophiomorpha nodosa* and *Planolites* are identifiable together with rare fossil shell remains (Plate 3). The presence of the aforementioned ichnofacies characterizes the influence of tidal or stressed estuarine environment. Also, the intensive bioturbation is an indication of lower shore face environment.

Plate 4- Fossiliferous sandy heterolith

Lithofacies 4: Fossiliferous Sandy heterolith. This sediment is observed in fine to very fine grained sandy strata. There is abundant shells debris which makes the lithofacies to be poorly sorted and is a major characteristic of the lithofacies (Plate 4). The clay content is high and could be noticed from the greyish-dark colour of the sandy heterolith. The lithofacies consists of climbing ripple lamination. Bioturbation activity is moderate to high, though the trace fossils encountered in the lithofacies include *Ophiomorpha* and *Skolithos* traces which occur sparingly. The very fine- to- fine grain size is an indication that it is deposited under low energy condition. The abundant shell debris shows the presence of shoreline setting while the trace fossils indicate shallow marine environment.

Plate 5- Wave rippled sandy heterolith

Lithofacies 5: Wave rippled sandy Heterolith. The lithofacies is composed of fine to very fine grained sand intercalated with draped dark grey mudstones (Plate 5). It is well sorted and well cemented. Bioturbation is moderate. There is the dominance of *Paleophycus* trace fossils; intercalation of sand with mud is an indication of bed load and suspension depositions. Wave ripple structure is an indication of low energy setting while marine assemblages of *Paleophycus* indicate a lower shoreface environment.

Plate 6- Current rippled sandy heterolith

Lithofacies 6: Current rippled sandy Heterolith. In this lithofacies, the sediments are well sorted. The grain sizes range from fine to very fine with current ripple bedding. These rippled sandstones are draped by wavy dark grey mudstones. The clay content in this lithofacies is observed to be moderate. There is a moderate occurrence of bioturbation activities, although there are restricted burrow traces of *Planolites* and *Skolithos* (Plate 6). Presence of well -sorted sand is an indication of low energy transportation while intercalation of sand and mud is a sign of bed load and suspension type of transportation and deposition. However, the restricted assemblages or burrows of the trace fossils is an indication of stressed environment as could be seen in mouth bars channels.

Plate-7 Bioturbated Sandy heterolith

Lithofacies 7: Bioturbated Sandy heterolith. The lithofacies consists of a heterolithic mixture of sand, silt and thin mudstone beds and laminae. It is well sorted with fine to very fine grain size ranges. The clay content moderate. Nodules of carbonate cement (probably of calcite composition) are present in the lithofacies. The sediment is highly bioturbated as such; there is complete destruction of primary sedimentary structures therein (Plate 7). The lithofacies is also parallel to wavy bedded and frequently distorted. Bioturbation is dominant with some patches of clay materials. The numerous burrow activities is an indication of deposition in a low energy shallow marine environment. The localized trace fossil assemblages indicate a stressed environment probably with a wave current action.

Plate 8- Cross -bedded sandstone

Lithofacies 8: Cross bedded sandstone. The sediment comprises medium to coarse-grained, poorly sorted grey sandstones. The sandstone constitutes a graded bed set and fines upwards with alternation of coarse and fine grain materials. This results to a bimodal grain size sorting (Plate 8). However, it becomes well sorted as it fines upwards and has trough cross-beds as the dominant primary sedimentary structures. The lithofacies also has an erosive basal.

Plate 9- Wavy bedded muddy heterolith

Lithofacies 9: Wavy bedded muddy heterolith. Wavy bedded muddy heterolith is made up of very fine grains of silt and clay, although the proportion of clay is greater than that of silt. It is greyish-dark in colour and well sorted. (Plate 9). The presence of siderite may be due to oxidation in a shallow marine setting. There are strong bioturbation activities while the trace fossil assemblages include *Paleophycus*, *Skolithos* and *Ophiomorpha*. However, the availability of sand and clay suggest deposition of both bed load and suspension load. Siderite indicates shallow marine condition while the trace fossils of *Paleophycus* (a sub-horizontal burrow) indicate a low energy lower shoreface environment.

Plate 10-Bioturbated muddy heteroliths

Lithofacies 10: Bioturbated muddy heteroliths. The sediments consist of very fine- to -fine grain silty shale deposits. The lithofacies (plate 10) has a sharp coarser base contact with sideritic bedded mudstone lithofacies. It is greyish in colour and well sorted. There is presence of ripple cross lamination. Bioturbation is moderate. Trace fossil content include *Planolites* and *Skolithos*, the presence of ichnofacies is an indication of marine condition. Ripple cross lamination is an indication of low energy environment. Absence of carbonaceous detritus is an indication of deoxygenation. The environment of deposition is therefore inferred to be that of offshore-transition.

Facies Association/Environment Of Deposition

Facies association reflects the combination of processes which occur in the depositional environment. From Walther's law, it is believed that if one facies is superimposed on another without a break, then the two facies would

have been deposited adjacent to each other at any one time in their geologic history. Thus, facies associations have genetic significance and could be identified as separate units using wireline logs and cores. Five facies associations and their environments are identified in the field of study using wells 6 and 7. The integrated interpretations of the facies association are hereby presented according to their vertical arrangement in the D7.000 sand starting from the base of the reservoir to the top.

Facies Association 1: The interval of this facies association on gamma ray log is between 12438 to 12391 ft and 12110 to 12060ft on wells 6 and 7 respectively. It is identified in the *gamma* ray log as D7₁ and is more extensive in well 6 than in well 7. The facies association is characterized by intensive wavy ripple structure and has a very fine- to -fine grain composition. Symmetrical and asymmetrical ripples exist locally. Examination of the core indicates that it has a gradational relationship with facies associations 2 above and the bottom seal below respectively. Facies association 1 is strongly to very strongly bioturbated. Trace fossils of Ophiomorpha and Paleophycus are common. It shows a funnel shape in gamma ray and bell shape in neutron density profile. Thus, there is a decrease in clay value upward.

Interpretation: Fine deposition indicates a low energy current while the dominance of wave rippled structures shows deposition in a wavy environment. However, the inter-lamination of siltstones and shales highlights deposition below wave base. Serrated nature of the gamma ray log is an indication of silty heteroliths, though bioturbation activity and diversity of fauna coupled with its gradational upward relationship with facies association 2 shows an influence of lower shoreface environment.

Facies Association 2: The facies association ranges in depth from 12391 to 12358ft and 12060 to 12024ft in wells 6 and 7 respectively. It is thicker in well 6 than in well 7. The major lithofacies that make up facies association 2 are hummocky stratified sandstone and planar laminated sandstone. There is a minor composition of wavy rippled sandstone. The grain size range in the facies association 2 is fine to medium, though it grades upwards to coarse planar cross- bedded sandstone, probably reflecting the base of a channel deposit. However, it grades downward into finer hummocky stratified sandstone. Sorting is moderate to poor. Bioturbation activity ranges from moderately bioturbated to none. However, there is the occurrence of sub-vertical ichnofacies burrows of Ophiomorpha nodosa and Skolithos. Traces of Planolites are also present. The hummocky cross -stratified sandstone is characterized by concave upward swales.

The gamma ray log as shown at a depth of about 12380 ft shows a coarsening upward pattern and low gamma ray value. The vertical facies sequence from the base to the top of these two sand bodies shows wave rippled sandstone and planar laminated sandstone. However, it comprises mainly hummocky stratified sandstone and a minor facies of wave rippled sandstone.

Interpretation: From the aforementioned characteristics, coarsening upward pattern is an indication of upward increase in energy. Hummocky cross stratification as a result of combined flow which occurs when a current is generated by a storm at the same time a high amplitude wave reaches down below the surface. Hummocky cross-stratification is a characteristic of the upper shoreface. High diversity of sub-vertical burrows of ichnofacies suggests high energy environment, that is above fair weather base or shallow marine. Sub-vertical burrows result from organisms that move up and down in the sediment with the changing water level of the shoreline. The facies association is therefore inferred to occur in a wave dominated upper shoreface environment.

Facies Association 3: This comprises facies association 3. The depth range of the facies association is 12358 to 12316 ft and 12024 to 12004 ft in wells 6 and 7 respectively. It is well developed and thicker in well 6 than in well 7. Facies association 3 is mainly made up of cross-bedded sandstone and wavy sandy heteroliths. Wave rippled sandstone could be a minor lithofacies in the association. The facies consist of medium to fine-grained sandstone and is poorly sorted, though there is little inter bedded mud drapes. It is characterized by fining upward sequence with an erosive base. Coarse grains are found at the erosive base. There is also an erosional truncation with the upper facies association 4. From the Gamma ray log, it is found to overlie the upper shoreface and has a bell shaped fining upward of grains and a positive separation of the neutron density logs. Bioturbation activity is rare. However, there is presence of sub-vertical and sub-horizontal burrows of Ophiomorpha and Planolites respectively. **INTERPRETATION:** The presence of coarse grains in the scoured or erosive base is an indication of a channel setting and the fining upward succession shows a decrease in energy of deposition upward and more likely an abandonment of channel lobe. The low diversity and presence of trace fossils of Ophiomorpha and Planolites is an indication of mixed energy environment. Therefore, facies association 3 is inferred to be a tidal deposit.

Facies Association 4: Facies association 4 occurs in the D.7000 sand. It has a depth range of 12316ft to 12256ft and 12004 to 11940 ft in wells 6 and 7, respectively. It is more sandy and well sorted in well 6 than in well 7. An integrated lithofacies description of the D.7000 sand from the base to the top shows that the major constituent lithofacies are coarse-grained cross bedded sandstone, current rippled sandstone, bioturbated sandstone and wave rippled sandstone. Though wavy muddy heteroliths and wavy sandy heteroliths may be available. The facies association is composed of fine to medium grain and moderately sorted sandstone. There are no depositions of mud drapes in this association. Due to lack of well sorting in the profile in well 7, there is a succession of both fining and coarsening upward trends in the lithofacies association of the D.7000 of well 7. Wavy muddy heteroliths and wavy sandy heteroliths do not occur in the D7000 of well 6.

Interpretation: The presence of dispersed coarse grains indicates tidal influence, carbonaceous detritus shows an organic presence. Planolites or presence of low diversity fauna signifies marine presence, probably paralic environment. Finally, scoured structure is an indication of a channel. Therefore, an amalgamated channel is inferred.

Facies Association 5: Facies association 5 occurs in the D7000 sand. The depth range of the facies association in well 7 is between 11940 and 11922 ft. In well 6, the facies association forms the major part of the uncored zone at a depth range of 12256to12220 ft. The main composing lithofacies are wavy muddy heteroliths and wavy sandy heteroliths. The facies association consists of fine to very fine materials of silt and clay sizes which signifies a low energy depositional environment. These particles are well sorted with wave rippled sedimentary and drape structures. It constitutes thin laminae sets. Mudstones occur as drapes between thinly laminated sand and silt. Bioturbation is rare, though some traces of sub-horizontal burrows of *Paleophycus* and *Planolites* are common.

Interpretation: The intercalation of fine and very fine materials is an indication of low energy, environment and occasional deposits of coarser materials is an evidence of tidal influence. Rare bioturbation activity shows stressed environment. The evidence of bipolar current, very fine deposits of mud, low diversity (stressed condition), suggest tidal flat environment.

Sequence Stratigraphy In 'Eme' Field

Studies are carried out to include the general sequence stratigraphy in the field of study, using the available biostratigraphic data and the Niger Delta chronostratigraphic Chart; three major maximum flooding surfaces and three sequence boundaries are delineated and named. Incidentally, sequence boundary occurs near the base of the D7.000 sand of study. These sequence boundaries show a recognizable erosive event across the field at the same stratigraphic level.

Interpretation:The maximum flooding surfaces in 'Eme' field using an integrated biostratigraphic data and Niger Delta chronostratigraphic chart, are within Chiloguembelina 3 and Ogara Shale. The age of Chiloguembelina 3 as seen in the field is 15.9 million years for its top while the base is 17.4 million years. The available data shows that Ogara shale with age 19.4 million years is encountered after the former at a greater depth. This is an indication of major episodes of marine incursion or transgression in the field. There is an inundation of the land by the sea and a land-ward shift in marine facies. This period witnessed the highest marine diversity and abundance in 'Eme' field at a depth of 12520 ft, 10000 ft and 7,660 ft.

Furthermore, with the inception of regressive phases in the field, sequence boundaries are formed at different times. Regression which led to progradation of facies or basin ward shift in facies causes erosion of the shelf. However, the ages of the three sequence boundaries identified in the field of study starting from the base of the two wells analyzed are 17.7my and 16.7my respectively. These points are seen as that with the lowest diversity and abundance of marine facies or the point of maximum regression in the field of study. The cycle of deposition in 'Eme' field is identified to be third order cycle. This is because the range of third order cycle is 1-10my (Reijers, 1996). However, the time difference from one sequence boundary in 'Eme' field to the nearest one falls within the range of 1-10my. Therefore, the order of cycle of sequence in the field of study is third order cycle.

Stratigraphic Sequence Of The D7.000 Sand: From the previous section, it is highlighted that sequence stratigraphic is as a result of increase or decrease in accommodation space. That means that, it is a function of sea level movement. From the wireline log response of a hydrocarbon bearing (D7.000) sand, maximum flooding surface is also known as that point that has a maximum positive separation on the neutron-density logs, highest gamma ray value and minimum resistivity, it represents a break in stratigraphic event and also has a chronostratigraphic value. Based on the position of these condensed sections on the D7.000 sand, only one stratigraphic sequence could be identified from the study of the reservoir sand. The sequence is interpreted starting from the base of the reservoir

(D7.000) sand of study.

From the biostratigraphic data, sequence boundary is identified near the base of the D7.000 sand. An integrated interpretation of the gamma ray logs of wells 6 and 7 indicates that the lower part of the D7.000 sand constitutes a progradational parasequence set.

There is a coarsening upward sequence and is separated from the upper part by an erosional surface. The depth interval of the progradational parasequence set in well 6 is between 12438 to 12358 ft and 12110 to 12024 ft in well 7. It constitutes the Highstand Systems (HST) Tract. There is occurrence of bottom seal, sand in the parasequence set. Furthermore, the upper part of the D7.000 sand is made up of retrogradational parasequence set. There is a fining upward sequence and it ends with a condensed section (top seal) at a depth of about 12164 ft. The depth interval of the upper retrogradational parasequence in well 6 is between 12358 to 12164 ft and 12024 to 11832 ft in well 7. The parasequence constitutes mainly Transgressive Systems (TST) Tract. The multi-storey sand bodies in this parasequence set from the base to the top are the D7₁, D7₃, D7₅, and D7₆. Therefore, only one stratigraphic sequence is identified in the D7.000 sand.

Reservoir Characterization.

The reservoir (D7.000) sand is composed of some good quality sandstones interbedded with mudstones. These mudstones act as permeability barriers to the vertical flow of hydrocarbon for this reservoir. The depositional sequence in the D7.000 sand is differentiated by change in grain sizes marked by mudstone facies. However, the occurrence of sandy heterolith in some parts of the reservoir could cause a differential flow in the lithological units. These lithological units may be in pressure communication with each other as a result of density contrast of the different depositional environment. From petrophysical property of the D7.000 sand obtained in well 6. Porosity and permeability values of the D7.000 sand are calculated using wireline logs of well 6. From the table of values, porosity is plotted against permeability (Fig 1). A very high decrease in porosity and permeability is an indication of low sand/shale ratio in the environment of deposition. High water fraction is an indication that the environment is not a potential for oil. From the gamma ray log of the D7.000 sand, the zone shows a gradation with the shelf mud. Hence, it is inferred to be part of the basal area (bottom seal) of the D7.000 sand or source of hydrocarbon. Finally, the rank of the interpreted depositional environments in terms of porosity and permeability from the best to the poorest is as follows: amalgamated channel, tidal channel, tidal deposit, upper shoreface and lower shoreface.

Figure 1: Porosity versus permeability Cross plot of the D7.000 Sand in 'Eme' Field.

Depositional Model of the D7.000 Sand

From the gamma ray log of the reservoir (D7.000) sand of study; the reservoir could be divided into two sequences based on the mode of deposition. These are the upper and lower part, i.e. the transgressive and regressive sections. Consequently, they are demarcated by an uncored mudstone layer at a depth of about 12352ft in well 6. However, the core gamma ray signature shows that the upper part of the lower D7.000 sand and the lower part of the upper D7.000 sand are not cored due to the muddy nature. Therefore, the reservoir model is considered along this line. The upper part which ranges in depth from 12352 to about 12150ft, consists of the following facies associations, namely from the base; tidal deposit, amalgamated channel, tidal flat, tidal channel, and marine shale. Therefore, the model will be that of transgressive estuarine system. Some of the sedimentary structures associated with the estuarine deposits are reactivation surfaces as a result of the influence of flood and ebb currents (bipolar current) on the sedimentary deposits. Couplets of sand and shale in heterolithic sequence and sporadic trace fossil assemblages with an increase in faunal diversity upward.

Furthermore, the lower regressive part of the reservoir sand of study ranges in depth from 12352 to 1252 ft. This lower part which forms a progradational sequence consists of the following facies associations starting from the base of the reservoir sand, offshore marine mud, lower shoreface and upper shoreface. The lower depositional sequence of D7.000 sand are deposits of a prograding wave dominated shallow marine shoreface setting. This interpretation is supported by the abundance of hummocky cross stratification structures, abundance of diverse marine trace fossils, and the upward decrease in diversity and population of these trace fossils. However, the two channel sandstones in the D7.000 reservoir have different geological properties and should be identified with different geological models. The tidal channel has a transgressive property, that is, it exhibits a fining upward sequence. Also, it has a gradational and erosional upper and lower contact respectively. Furthermore, in gamma ray log, it has a bell shape structure, while in the amalgamated channel of the upper retrogradational sequence, it has abrupt upper and lower erosional boundaries respectively, blocky gamma ray log signature and shows little or no separation in neutron-density logs.

In summary, the depositional model of the reservoir sand of study consists of the upper transgressive estuarine deposits and the lower progradational shallow marine sequence which is being influenced by the presence of bipolar currents involving wave/fluvial processes. A decrease in accommodation space results in a progradation of the facies belt across the shelf thereby giving rise to shelf deposits. Regression is consequently followed by a transgressive phase which resulted in the deposition of the upper part of the reservoir sand or the estuarine deposits. Hence, succession of sediment depositions in the reservoir sand of study involves a transgressive estuarine deposit overlying a progradational shallow marine shoreface deposits.

DISCUSSION

The D7.000 sand comprises sand body units. Each of these units is characterized by distinct lithofacies composition. However, some of the lithofacies appear in more than one sand body unit and are attributed to the transgressive and regressive movement of the sea.

Reineck et al. (1980) observed the lithofacies composition of both lower and upper shorefaces to be a range from fine sand to silty particles and fine to medium grain sand particles respectively. This is comparable to the lithofacies composition of the lower and upper shorefaces of the D7.000 sand. The lithofacies hummocky stratified sandstone present in the D7₂ is absent in the equivalent sand body (D7₁ unit. This may be as a result of the absence of stormy weather condition in the D7₁ which forms part of the tidal channel. Amajor et al 1990, in their study of Viking reservoir sandstone observed the vertical facies sequence of the marine facies from base to the top as prodelta facies, lower shoreface and upper shoreface, while the upper part of the reservoir constitutes transgressive estuarine deposits influenced by tidal current. The same depositional sequence is observed in the D7.000 sand and the prodelta facies is characterized by massive mudstone. The massive mudstone forms the bottom seal of the D7.000 sand.

Miall (1984) shows that the prodelta facies is as a result of suspension fallout in a low energy regime. Ichnofacies serve as water depth indicators and are valuable aid to the interpretation of sedimentary environments (Nichols, 1999). Hence, from the different sand body units in the D7.000 sand, distinct trace fossil assemblages are observed. For example, vertical burrows of *Ophiomorpha* and *Skolithos* trace fossils occur in the D7₂ sand unit. The animals that formed these trace fossils may have moved up and down in the sediment with the changing water level of the foreshore. There is no bioturbation activity seen in the massive mudstone of the bottom seal of the D7.000 sand. This may be attributed to the unfavorable conditions for organisms to thrive such as absence of light, food and oxygen in the environment.

CONCLUSION

The sequence stratigraphic setting of the D7.00 sand indicates the presence of a Sequence Boundary near the base of the sand body unit. Also only one stratigraphic sequence is identified. The Niger Delta chronostratigraphic chart indicates that the age of the Sequence Boundary is 20.4 my. However, in the course of this research work, the 'Order of Cycle' of deposition in 'Eme field is found to be 'third Order Cycle'. This is in support of Reijers, (1996) who identified a 'third Order Cycle' of deposition in the Niger Delta. Finally, from the core description done in the course of this research work, there is presence of tidal deposits, distributor mouth bar/upper shoreface deposits in the D7.000 sand. This is an indication that the upper D7.000 unit is a Transgressive System (TST) Tract and the lower portion is a Highstand Systems (HST) Tract.

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